

A large, stylized dome shape composed of purple dots and lines, identical to the logo in the top left corner.

CyberSecDome

CyberSecDome Open Call Proposal Template Round 1 - [Year]

Evaluation & Testing of Cybersecurity Solutions

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Introductory Guidance

This template is intended for applicants participating in the CyberSecDome Open Call. It has been designed to guide you in preparing a comprehensive proposal that addresses all required aspects for evaluation. Each section aligns with the evaluation criteria outlined in the CyberSecDome Open Call documentation: **Alignment, Excellence, Impact, Implementation, and Value for Money.**

Purpose of this Template

The structure of this template ensures that key aspects of your project are presented effectively, enabling evaluators to assess your proposal consistently and fairly. **Sections 1 through 5 correspond directly to the evaluation criteria** outlined in the CyberSecDome Open Call documentation:

1. **Alignment**
2. **Excellence**
3. **Impact**
4. **Implementation**
5. **Value for Money**

Each section is critical to demonstrating the quality, feasibility, and potential of your proposal. Proposals will be evaluated **as submitted**, without the possibility for major revisions during the grant preparation phase.

Important Instructions

1. Font and Formatting:

- **Font:** Calibri, size 11.
- **Spacing:** Single line, with 6pt paragraph spacing.
- **Margins:** Minimum of 15 mm on all sides.
- **Page Limit:** Maximum of **45** pages, including all sections, figures, and tables.
- **Language:** Proposals must be written in English.

2. Submission:

- Use this template as instructed.
- Proposals exceeding the page limit will have additional pages ignored during evaluation.
- Submit via the designated online portal before the deadline
- Remember to delete all instructions; templates and examples provided in this document before submission.
- Save your document in PDF format before final submission

Guidance on Using Generative AI Tools

Applicants may use generative AI tools to assist in the preparation of the proposal, provided that:

- All AI-generated content is reviewed for accuracy and compliance with intellectual property regulations.
- Any sources or citations generated by AI tools are double-checked for correctness and proper attribution.
- Applicants remain fully responsible for the proposal content, including acknowledging any limitations or biases introduced by AI tools.

1 General Information

Proposal Title:	
Acronym:	
Lead Applicant*:	
Contact Details:	

**In case of consortium please provide the name of the proposal coordinator*

2 Proposal Summary

Provide a high-level overview of your proposal, including:

- Objectives and relevance to CyberSecDome goals.*
- Expected outcomes and societal, economic, or technical impacts.*
- Key technologies, innovations, or methodologies to be applied. (Max 1000 characters)*

3 Applicant(s)Details

Applicant(s) Administrative information (including the consortium members -if applicable) is provided in the online application form system (Link). A summary list should also be provided in the table below.

Participant No*	Participant organisation name	Country
1. (Coordinator)		
2.		
3.		

**Please use the same participant numbering and name as that used in the administrative proposal forms*

4 Technical Description

4.1 Alignment

Note: *This section will be evaluated based on the "Alignment" criterion, which assesses how well the proposal aligns with the CyberSecDome objectives and challenges. Applicants must demonstrate their understanding of the project's scope, relevance to predefined topics, and alignment with CyberSecDome's strategic goals.*

4.1.1 Relevance to CyberSecDome Objectives:

- Explain how the proposal addresses the challenges and topics outlined in the Open Call.
- Clearly demonstrate alignment with CyberSecDome’s strategic objectives, focusing on AI and VR in cybersecurity.

4.1.2 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs):

- Define measurable and relevant KPIs.
- Show how KPIs align with the project’s goals and CyberSecDome’s expected outcomes.
- Feel free to use the template provided in Table 4-1 below

Table 4-1: KPIs Structure

Objective	KPI	Measurement Method	Target Value	Timeline
<i>E.g Improve user satisfaction with investigation tools</i>	<i>User satisfaction score from investigators</i>	<i>Feedback surveys and usability testing</i>	<i>Achieve a satisfaction score of 85/100</i>	<i>Month 8</i>

4.1.3 Fit with CyberSecDome Framework:

- Describe how the solution integrates with existing CyberSecDome architectures and technologies.
- Highlight any enhancements or gaps addressed by the proposal.

4.2 Excellence

Note: This section corresponds to the "Excellence" criterion, focusing on the scientific and technical innovation of the proposal. Evaluators will assess the clarity and ambition of the objectives, the soundness and novelty of the methodology, and the project’s potential to advance the state of the art.

4.2.1 Objectives and Ambition:

- State the specific objectives of the project and their relevance to the CyberSecDome framework.
- Highlight any innovative approaches or methodologies used.
- Explain how the proposal advances the state-of-the-art in cybersecurity.

4.2.2 Methodology:

- Describe the scientific and technical soundness of your approach.
- Detail concepts, models, and assumptions underpinning the work.
- Demonstrate how the interdisciplinary or multi-sectoral approach enhances feasibility.

4.2.3 Open Science and Ethical Considerations:

- Include plans for sharing research outputs and ensuring ethical compliance, especially concerning data privacy and AI ethics.

4.3 Impact

Note: This section is linked to the "Impact" criterion, which evaluates the proposal’s potential to deliver significant benefits to the cybersecurity ecosystem. Applicants must outline their pathway to impact, including dissemination, exploitation, and sustainability plans, as well as metrics for measuring success.

4.3.1 Pathway to Impact:

- Explain how the project’s results contribute to CyberSecDome objectives and wider cybersecurity advancements.
- Define target groups and quantify expected impacts (e.g., reduced threat detection time).
- Feel free to use the template of Table 4-2 below to present this subsection in a structured way

Table 4-2: Pathway to Impact

Impact Category	Description	Target Groups	Expected Outcomes
[Societal/ Economic/ Technical]		[e.g Public Sector/ Private Sector/ Cybersecurity Professionals /Academic and Research Communities/ General Public and Civil Society/ Policymakers and Regulators/ Technology Providers and Innovators]	

4.3.2 Dissemination and Exploitation Plans:

- Outline dissemination strategies for reaching key stakeholders (scientific community, businesses, policymakers).
- Detail exploitation strategies for project results, including potential partnerships or commercialisation pathways.
- Feel free to use Table 4-3 or Table 4-4 in case of consortium to present your plan in a structured way.

Table 4-3: Dissemination & Exploitation Plan

Dissemination/Exploitation Activity	Target Audience	Purpose	Timeline

Table 4-4: Dissemination & Exploitation Plan (Consortium version)

Dissemination/Exploitation Activity	Target Audience	Purpose	Timeline	Responsible Partner

4.3.3 Sustainability:

- Provide a sustainability plan for outcomes beyond project funding.
- Address scalability and adaptability of the results.

4.3.4 Monitoring and KPIs:

- Include KPIs to track progress and evaluate impacts.
- Highlight feedback loops to improve results during and after implementation.
- Feel free to use Table 4-5 or Table 4-6 in case of consortium to present your plan in a structured way.

Table 4-5: Impact KPIs Monitoring

KPI	Description	Target Value	Measurement Method	Timeframe for Monitoring

Table 4-6: Impact KPIs Monitoring (Consortium Version)

KPI	Description	Target Value	Measurement Method	Timeframe for Monitoring	Responsible Entity

5 Implementation

Note: This section addresses the "Implementation" criterion, which focuses on the feasibility and quality of the work plan, the appropriateness of resource allocation, and risk management strategies. Evaluators will also assess the team’s capacity to deliver the project successfully.

5.1.1 Work Plan and Structure:

- Present the overall work plan, including a Gantt chart of timelines and milestones.
- Include detailed work package descriptions with tasks, deliverables, and interdependencies.
- Feel free to use Table 5-1 which provides a holistic view of all elements in WPx. It includes tasks, deliverables, and milestones in a unified format, ensuring clarity and consistency.

Table 5-1: WPx Description

WP [XX] – [Title of WP]	Duration in Months: [Mxx – Mxy]
Lead Partner: [ACRONYM]	Contributors [ACRONYM 1, ACRONYM2]
Objectives	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OBJ1.x • ... • OBJ1.y 	
Tasks	
Tx.x – “Task Title”	Lead: [ACRONYM] , Contribution: [ACRONYM1, ACRONYM 2]
[Task Description]	
Tx.y – “Task Title”	Lead: [ACRONYM], Contribution: [ACRONYM1, ACRONYM 2]
[Task Description]	
Deliverables	
Dxx - “Deliverable Title”; Leader: [ACRONYM]; Mxx	Description of Deliverable Dxx

<i>Dxy - "Deliverable Title"; Leader: [ACRONYM]; Mxx</i>	<i>Description of Deliverable Dxy</i>
<i>Dxz - "Deliverable Title"; Leader: [ACRONYM]; Mxx</i>	<i>Description of Deliverable Dxz</i>
Milestones	
<i>MSxx – Milestone Title; Mxx</i>	<i>Milestone Description</i>
<i>MSxx – Milestone Title; Mxx</i>	<i>Milestone Description</i>

5.1.2 Resource Allocation and Budget:

- *Justify resource needs, including personnel, equipment, and financial allocations.*
- *Provide a table summarising person-months and resource distribution.*

5.1.3 Risk Management:

- *Identify risks and propose mitigation strategies. Categorise risks by likelihood and severity.*

5.1.4 Management and Coordination:

- *Outline the project’s management structure, decision-making processes, and reporting mechanisms.*

6 Budget and Funding

Note: *This section will be evaluated under the "Value for Money" criterion. It examines whether the requested funding is justified, cost-effective, and aligned with the project’s objectives. Applicants must demonstrate efficient use of resources, provide budget transparency, and outline any additional contributions or synergies.*

6.1.1 Budget Justification:

- *Details how each cost item is directly linked to the project's objectives and deliverables.*
- *Explains why the budget is reasonable and necessary to achieve project goals.*

6.1.2 Cost-Effectiveness:

- *Demonstrates how resources will be used efficiently.*
- *Provides metrics to show the expected return on investment (e.g., improvements in cybersecurity capabilities relative to costs).*

6.1.3 Leveraging Additional Resources:

- *Highlights contributions from external sources (e.g., partnerships, co-financing, in-kind contributions) to enhance the project’s impact.*

6.1.4 Transparency and Accountability:

- *Explains the distribution of resources among partners or within the team.*
- *Ensures transparency in funding allocation.*

6.1.5 KPIs for Value for Money:

- *Although this might overlap with monitoring metrics, it is essential to provide specific indicators related to cost-effectiveness (e.g., cost savings per threat mitigated or scalability improvements achieved for a given budget).*

6.2 Detailed Budget Table

Purpose:

This subsection provides a detailed breakdown of the project budget. Applicants must complete the provided budget table template, outlining all eligible costs and aligning them with the project's objectives, work plan, and deliverables. This table will be evaluated under the "Value for Money" criterion.

Instructions:

Applicants are required to:

- *Use the budget table template provided below.*
- *Provide a clear and detailed breakdown of all costs across the following categories:*
 - *Personnel*
 - *Equipment*
 - *Travel*
 - *Subcontracting*
 - *Other Direct Costs*
 - *Indirect Costs (25%)*
- *Ensure all costs are justified and directly linked to the activities described in the proposal.*

Additional Notes:

- *Ensure the budget reflects cost-effectiveness and efficient use of resources.*
- *For consortium proposals, clearly indicate the distribution of costs among partners, including any subcontracting or in-kind contributions.*
- *Provide a brief justification for any significant cost items in the narrative under Section 6.1.1 (Budget Justification).*

Template:

The budget table should follow the format of Table 6-1 below. It must include the cost breakdown for each partner (if applicable) and align with the work packages outlined in the implementation section.

Table 6-1: Estimated Budget Breakdown

Cost Category	Description	Estimated Cost (€)
Personnel		
Equipment		
Travel		
Subcontracting		
Other Direct Costs		
Indirect Costs (25%)		
Total		

Note: *Ensure that all cost estimates are justified and align with the project's objectives and work plan as described in earlier sections.*

7 Ethical Considerations

Note: *This section will be evaluated based on the "Alignment" criterion, which assesses how well the proposal aligns with the CyberSecDome objectives and challenges. Applicants must demonstrate their understanding of the project's scope, relevance to predefined topics, and alignment with CyberSecDome's strategic goals.*

- *Address ethical issues, including data privacy, security, and societal impacts.*
- *Demonstrate compliance with EU regulations and principles, including those on the use of AI technologies.*

Appendices

General Notes for Applicants:

- *Appendices should not exceed **25 pages in total***
- *Keep the content concise and relevant to avoid overwhelming evaluators with unnecessary details.*
- *Refer to appendices within the main proposal (e.g., "See Appendix 3 for CVs of key personnel") to ensure they are reviewed in context.*

Delete Instructions Before Submission